
The Rohingya Refugee Crisis: Socio-Economic, and Environmental Impacts on Local Community in Bangladesh

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Abstract: *Rohingya is a Muslim minority ethnic group that suffered persecution in Myanmar. The Myanmar government has rejected their citizenships. Since 1970, Rohingya has been compelled to flee their territory to Bangladesh in different forms because of ethnic, economic, and political discrimination. Bangladesh has since been faced with a continuing severe refugee crisis. Nearly one million Rohingya remained in several settlements and regions in Chittagong, Bangladesh. This region of refugees is unbearable for the people of Bangladesh and the state. Bangladesh has been taking Rohingya refugees from Myanmar since the 70s. Still now Bangladesh is sheltering, feeding, and providing various assistance to well over a million refugees. Bangladesh is an overpopulated country. The population density is about 1252 per square kilometer in Bangladesh, and the population growth rate is 1.03%. Bangladesh is facing different kinds of challenges. These challenges are economic, social, and environmental. Bangladesh lost numerous trees, forests and mountains in the Chittagong district as a result of the vast flood of Rohingya refugees. Rohingya refugees are increasing local prices due to their numbers and demand. Thus, there are overall socio-economic issues related to Rohingya refugees in Bangladesh, and this study examined a socio-economic context, environmental problems, and implications of abuse of natural resources before August 2017 in Cox's Bazar. The findings suggest that the decades of refugees in Cox's Bazar have both positive and negative consequences. Numerous positive benefits entail changes in social services, expansion of the market, growth in small businesses and new living opportunities. The analysis shows that the negative outcomes of the crisis outweigh the beneficial effect, which leads to local instability and tensions.*

Keywords: *Community, Impacts, Socio-Economy, Bangladesh, Myanmar, Environment, Security, Refugee crisis*

Aims of the study

This study describes the economic, social, and environmental effects of Rohingya influxes mostly on the local Bangladeshi population (Chittagong) and the complexity of addressing the government's challenge. This study aims at assessing and dissecting the impact on the present host population of Rohingya refugees. This research also helps to understand how people see a big number of refugees. The findings of this study describe the impact of the number of refugees on hosts and the host community experience of Rohingya refugees in Bangladesh.

Contribution of the Study

The Government of Bangladesh, with the assistance of the public and the United Nations, regularly supported humanitarian aid in Bangladesh. Over 200,000 refugees from Rohingya left Myanmar in 1978 and reached Bangladesh for the very first time. The Bangladeshi Government has built 20 camps for all Rohingya refugees in Bandarban and Cox's Bazar. The Bangladeshi Government has over several decades been highly liberal towards Rohingya refugees. And now the administration's compassion and assets face massive pressure, with new problems linked to security, and the deforestation divergence between the local community and refugees. An immediate and practical approach to the refugee problem is expected between the local community and refugees. This study will look into these critical issues that are presently missing from the abundance of literature that is available on the subject. The research enables to analyze the influence of the rapid expansion of the 2018 refugee crisis on the host communities of Cox's Bazar in literature review on the Rohingya issue.

Research Question

1. How does the local host community affect the arrival in Bangladesh of the Rohingya refugee?
2. Why does the flood of Rohingya harm the host culture, economy and security in Bangladesh for Rohingya refugees?

Methodology

It is a qualitative secondary-data analysis. Data were gathered from books, peer-reviewed journal publications, global, government and NGO studies, websites, International, and local newspapers, etc.

1. Introduction

A prominent political and ethical problem in current Bangladesh is the marginalization of the thousands of refugees who are at danger and humiliated every day. In addition to the apparent threat of routine war visibility, there would also be the risk of sanctuary reluctance and lasting uncertainty. Their challenges represent the reality that each will have their condition in a system of nation-states (Getrell, 2017). About 70.8 million people have been forced to move, nearly 25.9 million of whom are refugees under the age of eighteen. Millions of stateless citizens are still denied a nationality and fundamental rights such as education, health care, jobs and freedom of travel (UNHCR, 2018). According to Amnesty International, there are 25.9 million refugees now in the world. Half the world's refugees are infants. A third of the refugees, 6.7 million, are hosted by the poorest countries in the world. Around 1.4 million refugees, who are particularly vulnerable and need to be relocated on an ongoing basis, but in 2018 only 92,400 refugees were resettled and less than 7% of those awaiting relocation (Amnesty International, 2020). The UN estimated in February 2018 that over 1,000,000 Rohingya refugees escaped the horrific extermination operation in Burma. In Cox's Bazar, Bangladesh, they migrated almost resoundingly to refugee camps. It emphasizes Bangladesh, where a significant number of people were consumed in just six months, and the camp

environments were not suitable. Bangladesh is a poor, weaker, over-crowded nation, with politicians and citizens deeply displeased by the Rohingya refugee incursion from Burma. Complete global assistance is given to refugees and does not include all the economic consequences of the Bangladeshi residents of the state or the border area. Coastal town and Cox's Bazar beaches were formerly the critical attractions for visitors in Bangladesh; now that it's full of international relief organizations. While vaccination in Bangladesh has been accessible in rural communities for a long time, health experts are concerned that settlements propagate bacterial and other infectious diseases (Alam, 2018). The study assesses the impact of Rohingya refugee inrush mostly on residents' culture, trying to bridge the gap in empirical work. This work reflects on the effects of Bangladesh's policy on local society and limited capital, under international community auspices. While the Rohingya existed in Myanmar for decades, they were officially deprived of their nationality in 1982 and declared unregistered. Government officials limit their travel. Over 90,000 Rohingya people had escaped Myanmar since October when the army started a crackdown on what it called Rohingya militants after an attack on an army barracks. Thousands of Rohingya civilians have been killed since. The UN has suspected Burma of international crimes. The influx of refugees has remained in Bangladesh since the 1970s. The totals differ between 300,000 and 500,000. Most centres for refugees are built off the Teknaf-Cox Bazar highway all along the Naf River between Bangladesh and Myanmar. (Husein, 2020).

2. Historical Background of Rohingya

The Rohingya are an ethnic community, a large part of whom are Muslims, who spent decades in Buddhist Myanmar. Ruaingga is the language of Rohingya people, this language is unique from the other languages spoken everywhere in Myanmar. Rohingya are not listed as one of the country's 135 valid ethnic minorities, and since 1982, Myanmar has refused citizenship, making them stateless. Approximately all Rohingya live in Rakhine, and can not leave without government permission (Milko, 2019). Myanmar is located near the Bay of Bengal, and even in the 7th century, Arakan was the commercial hub. And Arakan has been the essential element for different cultures between Myanmar and the outside globe. The Arakan zone was the benchmark for seventh-century businesses. Many Arab, Moghul, and Moor Muslim traders reached in this area in the 7th century for business, and they settled here. According to Walton, "The origins of the Rohingya in Arakan, Myanmar are well documented in the literature and are said to date from the 7th century AD. Their ancestry can be traced to Arab, Moor, Pathan, Moghul, Central Asian, and Indo-Mongoloid people who settled in the region over several centuries" (Walton, 2014). When the Arab traders reached in this area, they started to preach their religion in the Arakan region and converted many people to Islam. Thus they made Arakan as a secure zone of the Muslim community. The Arab merchants were preachers, and around 788 CE started to convert the local Buddhist community into Islam. If we sincerely look at Rohingya society, we can easily find out their origin by their name, culture & tradition. According to Siddique, "Today, Rohingya display considerable cultural diversity but still carry Arab names, Muslim faith, and traditional customs. As such, they are regarded by some ethnologists, anthropologists, and linguists as a distinct indigenous race of Burma; however, others question the legitimacy of their identity" (Siddique, 2012).

3. The Influx of Rohingya Refugees in Bangladesh

The total geographical area of Cox Bazar is around 2491,32 km², and the entire population is about 22,890,990 km. For the first time, local people generally welcomed the Rohingya refugees,

but there has recently been an anti-refugee sentiment. According to Milton, "Refugee camps are mostly situated in remote areas where the economic circumstance of local inhabitants is not stable. Consequently, there is an anti-Rohingya sentiment generated among local people due to the competition that has been created in the local livelihood sector by the burden of refugees" (Milton, 2017). Current government of Bangladesh reported that approximately 200,000-500,000 unidentified Rohingya refugees remained in neighboring villages before the wave of violence in Myanmar, 2017. Together, 33,131 registered refugees lived in two state-organized camps (Milton, 2017).

The numbers of Rohingya Refugee in Cox's Bazar as at April 2018

Camp name	Number of Rohingya
Kutupalong refugee camp	13,933
Kutupalong expansion	604,104
Hakimpara	31,280
Jamtoli	46,196
Bagghona	22,076
Chakmarkul	12,597
Unchiprang	22,100
Leda MS	9,800
Nayapara RC	19,353
Thangkhali	43,500

Source: www.unocha.org, 2018

4. Literature Review

In the host state, rapid, unpredictable flows of refugees may cause significant disturbance to weak ecological balance, leading to economic and social varieties (Lee, 2005). Several studies have been conducted mostly on the host community's impacts and effects of refugees. Such studies mostly had economic implications as acceptance of refugees had both negative positive and economic results. Foreign aid agencies create more jobs in the host community, and it is also a local school, clinic and accommodation project (Jacobsen, 2012). A critical study by Kobia and Cranfield shows that refugees could be at risk since they are under stress if unemployed, but if they are employed, they fear local workers (Kobia, 2009). Refugees often sell their aid at a low price that influences local small retailers because they can't interact with refugees who have lower tax or rental costs (Mogire, 2011). The Rohingya crisis triggered a significant effect on the tourism market

between the refugee camp of Cox's Bazar and other areas more north of Bangladesh (Lewis, 2018). The massive arrival of refugees raises competition for fundamental commodities, including food. Source of refugee assistance perceives whether prices of these essential products decrease or increase. International aid demonstrates lower price force, while aid from various sources generates rising market pressure. If supply could not fulfil stiff competition in commodities, price increases would further impair the population of the host state (Alix-Garcia, 2009). Security issues have become an essential issue in the accommodation of refugees and host communities because refugees are engaged in numerous illegal activities. Refugees frequently clash directly against residents by violating the local rule of law and pose a direct danger to local citizens (Mogire, 2011). Rohingya may wish to join such terrorist groups as the Jama'atul Mujahideen Bangladesh, Rohingya Solidarity Organization or Harkat-ul-Jihad-al Islam. They could be a danger to regional and national protection (Wolf, 2014). They are also sensitive to fraudulent local politicians using Rohingya refugees to serve their interests criminal ambition such interactions can pose a security challenge for government entities (Islam, 2017). According to Wolf study, the Rohingyas seemed partially responsible for the rise of the religious extremists in Bangladesh from 1992 onwards (Wolf, 2014). According to research by Mogire, there are six Refugee and local society conflict reasons 1) The competition between refugees and local for land and fuelwood host 2) Environmental misapplication causes conflict between refugees and host communities by refugees, such as degradation and emissions 3) Intense competition in assets and incentives is a significant conflict origin 4) When refugees interfere in the host country's internal violence and start participating in this controversy 5) Local people interpret unfairness about the assistance that refugees from the various international organizations receive, and residents regard them as equally deserving of receiving similar aid. The ultimate cause of friction is the lack of understanding of the difference in culture between local people and refugees (Mogire, 2011). The massive flood of refugees has a significant adverse effect on the climate and other tools (UNHCR, 1996). The enormous rise in population means that large quantities of trees are cut off for housing and cooking fuel, resulting in degradation (Martin, 2005). According to the study of Adhikary, environmental issues occur in the deterioration of forestland, groundwater supplies, the disruption of land flows and wildlife in the refuges. In addition to the vulnerable ecosystems, the use of natural forests leads to an increase in the social conflict between the host and the Rohingyas (Adhikary, 2018). It is hard to accommodate them inside refugee centres because of the size of the current Rohingya influx. Key environmental issues include camp integrated health, water contamination, degradation and overuse of ecologically responsible assets that affect the native people's lives (Datta, 2015). Among these overcrowded and dangerous camps, diseases such as HIV, diarrhoea and cholera also spread with other infectious diseases, which can also affect residents and refugees. (Atim, 2013).

5. The Impacts of Rohingya refugees on the local community in Bangladesh

5.1. Price Hiking and Food Security

Bangladesh needs to spend 712,600 Trillion Taka annually on behalf of the Rohingya refugees. Bangladesh is considered to have a tremendous economic impact unless it is allowed to settle rapidly in Myanmar (Ahmed, 2020). The impacts of Rohingya refugees contain local food shortages, food supply scarcity, hiking necessary and transportation costs, natural resources, and tourism burdens, along with lots of social issues (Maahmud, 2017). The supplies required in this area are limited. As a result, the local population's ordinary lives are interrupted. The rejectors

would not be permitted to work as per the rules. But they've been involved in a variety of tasks, such as salt sectors, hatcheries, and small farms. Local poor labourers are slowly becoming unemployed (Khan, 2017). There is no food shortage in Bangladesh as a whole, but the inhabitants of Cox's Bazar are in threat because of Rohingya refugees (Alam, 2018). Due to a vast rise in demand for food and other goods and the anticipated shortage of supply, the price increase has touched everyone in the country (Rashid, 2019). The rising price of food, especially in Cox's Bazar, is a big challenge to the national economy of Bangladesh every day. Under such situations, not only Rohingya but also the native population need foreign food assistance (Khatun, 2018). For the Rohingya refugees, regular food prices have increased by approximately 50 percent; day labour incomes also dropped, some 2,500 households even lost under the poverty line. The poverty in the local community has risen by almost three percent (Hashim, 2019). Price hiking is now a serious issue, and day by day, it's creating an imbalance in the local market. Dhaka Tribune published a report in 2017, "As of Monday, per kilogram onion was sold at Tk60 and potato at Tk40 at Ukhiya. Both items were sold at Tk45 and Tk25, respectively, in Dhaka" (Bhuiyan, 2019).

Price situation (USD) of important goods in Bangladesh, 2018

Food Item	Pre-inflow	Post-inflow
Rice	0.38	0.45
Fish (Fresh Water)	1.53	1.76
Meat (Beef)	5.18	5.88
Salt	0.26	0.29
Sugar (Gur)	0.71	0.73
Flour	0.33	0.41
Lentils	1.18	1.10
Edible Oil	1.18	1.10
Potato	0.26	0.35
Other Vegetables	0.29	0.35

Source: UNDP household survey, 2018

5.2. Impacts on Tourism

The port town and the beaches of Cox's Bazar have always been Bangladesh's top tourist locations; the region is now teeming with international aid employees (Alam, 2018). As the exodus of Rohingya refugees continues apace, Cox's Bazar-based tourist industry has been depressed by a lengthy crisis. Travellers also decline their plans to travel to St Martin's Island in the Bay of Bengal caused by a combination of wounded refugees in Teknaf. This amounts, in fact, with a double-edged sword for the travel companies (The Financial Express, 2017). Cox's Bazar tourism business

is in threat if Rohingya's situation is to be extended. Cox's Bazaar is becoming a very populated area for Rohingya refugees. If the issues of the Rohingya continue, many travellers can turn from Cox's Bazar to another tourist spot. It will impact the local and national economy (Myat, 2018). Rohingya refugees moving all over the district are sure to threaten tourism as travellers are afraid to visit because of security problems and instability (Bhuiyan, 2017). Due to the continued condition of uncertainty, the number of visitors travelling to the area has significantly reduced. Travel agencies predict they might lose over half a million visitors this period (Khan, 2017). Because of the Rohingya evacuation, the hotel industry in the local area is suffering because they stated a reduction of around 40 percent in hotel bookings, although in the period of their products compared to the prior year (The Daily New Nation, 2017).

5.3. Security, Prostitution and Trafficking

The dispute between the local community and refugee communities is widespread (Chambers, 1986). The refugee crisis in Rohingya is no longer a single humanitarian problem but presents a potential risk to Bangladesh's domestic stability and security and may pose a growing challenge to multinational stability in the South East Asian zone (BIPSS, 2017). The jihadist group of ARSA is already able to attract jihadist soldiers to cross-border fighting and trafficking of military weapons and narcotics from refugee camps who are undermining law order and protection (Haque, 2016). Rohingyas are now entering the Middle East secretly with a Bangladeshi nationality and a birth certificate. Their involvement in various illegal activities was recorded in many assessments and widespread media reporting, which raised an international problem for Bangladesh (Imran, 2014). Trafficking has been prominent in Cox's Bazar refugee camps (Coorlim, 2019). The influx of Rohingya has created a variety of other social anxieties, including engagement in guns and drug trade, human smuggling, criminal conduct, and prostitution in Cox's Bazar zone (Uddin, 2012). Rohingya women are frequently involved in drug smuggling, and sex work and these criminal activities harm Bangladesh (Iqbal, 2017). The Fortify Rights Organization, and Human Rights Commission of Malaysia investigated that Over 170,000 people boarded boats from Myanmar and Bangladesh heading for Malaysia and Thailand during 2012-15, and trafficking over Rohingyas is calculated to have created between \$50 million and \$100 million a year. It disclosed that the smugglers had piled hundreds and even thousands of Rohingya refugees into processed fishing boats and stripped them of sufficient food, water and energy, murder and, in several cases, sexual assault at sea. Members of a gang kidnapped, murdered, abused, and otherwise exploited countless numbers of people, women, and kids, in several cases deliberately buying and selling them in partnership with state officials (Palma, 2019). In Bangladesh's Rohingya refugee camps, girls in their early teenage years are forced into prostitution. Foreigners looking for sex could quickly gain access to kids who have escaped the Myanmar clash (BBC, 2018). Trafficked Rohingya women might finish up with a life of prostitution, imposed labour by boys; many are trafficked to India (Coorlim, 2019). BBC News shared a story of a Rohingya woman; She is Anwara(14). After her parents had been killed, she left Myanmar looking for protection on the way to Bangladesh. She stated, "Women came with something like a van, asking me if I would go along with them." She was packed into something like a car after welcoming their assistance, with the hope of a safe passage to a new life. Instead, she was brought to Cox's Bazar, the closest town. Anwara claimed, "not much later they gave me two people. They handed me a knife and stabbed me through my stomach and assaulted me for not cooperating. Otherwise, the guys would rap me. I didn't want to have sex, but both continued" (BBC, 2018). Iqbal shared another story of a Rohingya woman in

November 2017, her name was Halima and shared her experiences to BBC News, Until being saved by Bangladesh police, she was forced into prostitution for two months. She was involved in prostitution again; however, because she had no capital or assistance (Iqbal, 2017).

5.4. Drugs and Smuggling

Drugs named 'Yaba' locally are not only a regional issue in the Chittagong area, but they have also been shown in a few years to be the most popular drug in Bangladesh. Approximately 740,000 Rohingya came to Bangladesh after such a government crackdown in Myanmar in August 2017, and drug smuggling has now become a severe problem in Cox's Bazar refugee camps where they stay. Al Jazeera reported the news in 2019; The Bangladeshi Police have detained a Rohingya man in their largest drug dealer that year with \$5 million of heroin tablets (Al Jazeera, 2019). Reuters also shared a speech of a woman who is Morijam. She sits on a women's committee, set up by the International Organization for Migrants (IOM) to help the Rohingya women, she said, "Yaba is in camps all around the place, and drugs are popular. We want to get the military to stop selling Yaba" (Karim, 2019). Dhaka Tribune published news in 2017 that more than 500 yaba traders have arrived from Myanmar to Bangladesh since August 25 by identifying as Rohingya refugees. This news also mentioned a report of the Association for the Prevention of Drug Abuse that Approximately 90% of yaba packets reach Bangladesh via the Naf River. Security agencies have confiscated over 500,000 sets of yaba tablets since August 25, 2017, and detained 70 persons, who are mostly Rohingyas according to Cox's Bazar district police. Drug smugglers of whom have arrived in Bangladesh already hide in the Rohingya camps and commit serious crimes when feasible (Maahmud, 2017).

5.5. Environmental Impacts of Rohingya Refugees on the Local Community

Ecological degradation has been one of Bangladesh's most significant issues for years, and the Rohingya storm has undoubtedly stepped up these challenges (The Daily Sun, 2019). UNHCR's Environmental Guidelines of 1996 stated that Refugees could harm the environment of host communities by the following six types: the destruction of natural resources; cumulative impacts on natural resources; health risks; social effects on local communities and economic effects (Martin, 2005). The ecological damage of the refugee residential areas is connected to camp settlement deterioration. Woods must be used for housing and also as firewood for heating (Mogire, 2011). In total 3,713 hectares of forest land, the Rohingya temporary settlements were captured under the Ukhia, Whykong and Teknaf reserves. Intrusion includes 1,960 acres of woodland and 1,753 acres of farmland (Hasan, 2019). Bangladesh has been battling environmental destruction challenges due to years of refugee flood, but the current wave of refugees has been far more significant. Several of the vital ecological effects culminating from those in the existence of Rohingya are the total absence of drinking water availability and suitable waste disposal in the event of natural calamities (Ahmed, 2018). According to the CPD report, The Rohingya camps have damaged roughly 6,000 acres of land. This is the total of 741.3 or 86.7 million crores. Around 6880 tons of fuelwood is required for the Rohingya in a month. If this amount is captured, 90 percent of the forests will stop within a 10 km buffer zone. This stock of fuelwood impacts the surrounding Teknaf Nature reserve, Inani Sea Beach and Himchari National Park (Khatun, 2017). The Daily Star reported the news in July 2018; The environmental problems are not only inside as well as outside of the camps. The increased

dependency on fuelwood for heating leads to the continued destruction of trees outside of the villages, contributing and not only to woodland depletion as well as to habitat loss (Huq, 2018).

Demand for biomass and fuelwood of Rohingya in the influx area, Cox’s Bazar, Bangladesh

Parameter	Buffer of 5 km	Buffer of 10 km
Total biomass available from natural forest (tons)	28,100	74,300
Total biomass available from plantations	124,100	211,600
Biomass required for 650,000 Rohingya (tons/month)	6,825	6,825
Time required to consume all available fuelwood from natural forest	4 months	11 months
Time required to consume all available fuelwood from plantations	18 months	31 months

Source: Rapid Environmental Impact Assessment done by UNDP, and MoEF, 2017. Cited by Khatun, 2018

UNDP and UN Women published a study in 2018 that Ukhia and Teknaf of Cox's Bazar lost over 4,300 acres of forests and mountains demolished to build buildings, utilities and cooking fuel. About half of the region's total natural woodland has been occupied. About 3,000 to 4,000 acres of wild terrestrial plants have already been destroyed in the Teknaf-Ukhia-Himchari trouble region (Uddin, 2019). Air pollution severely worsened together across camp routes throughout the streamflow zone leading to excessive traffic. Cooking camp indoor air emissions are of particular concern for children and women. Almost all of the physical effects are probable to be placed inside or close to the density of the camps. They can't act cumulatively with similar results from other tasks in the region (Khatun, 2018).

Environmental warning for physical issue at Rohingya Camp Areas, Cox’s Bazar, Bangladesh

Potential Risk	Impact	Reversible
Air Quality		
Impact of cooking on the indoor air quality	Severe	Yes
Dust generation	Moderate	Yes
Air pollution from transport	Minor	Yes
Acoustic Environment		
Noise from road transport	Minor	Yes
Ground Water		

Groundwater depletion	Critical	Not in short time
Groundwater contamination	Critical	Not in short time
Surface Water		
Change in water quality	Moderate	Yes
Change in hydrology	Moderate	Yes
Soils and Terrain		
Soil removal and erosion	Severe	No
Soil Diversity	Moderate	Not in short time
Land capability	Severe	Not in short time
Change in the terrain that may cause landslides	Severe	No
Sewer sludge Management	Critical	Yes
Solid Waste Management	Critical	Yes

Source: Rapid Environmental Impact Assessment done by UNDP, and MoEF, 2017. Cited by Khatun, 2018

6. Conclusion

The situation of refugees around the modern world is the alarming warning of the powerlessness to oppress, brutality and harass the individuals who are causing them to leave their homes through global human rights fraternity, folksy states and humanitarian assistance delegation. While one of the broader global issues, the Rohingya crisis as well as its impacts on Bangladesh have been one of the world's largest humanitarian crises worldwide. The goal of this study was to assess the injurious impacts of refugee flows on the local people of Bangladesh. Different pieces of literature have been used and showed the flood of refugees to Bangladesh from August 2017, as the present situation became one of the most significant rising refugee emergencies.

The study seeks to analyse the influence of a big number of Rohingya on the host people in Cox's Bazar, Chittagong. The Rohingya problem is a terrible issue for Bangladesh. All worry about the mass influx of Rohingya in Bangladesh, deep-term adverse impacts on society in Bangladesh. The harmful results of accommodating so many residents in some hill regions have negatively affected the regional economy. These impacts of Rohingya refugees are reaching now to the local and international level very fast. The influx of Rohingya refugees is challenged now for the environmental imbalance in Chittagong. Most of the refugee camps are settled in Chittagong Forest Reserve area. Local community and Rohingya refugees have to collect firewood for their survival. But the reserve forest area is not sufficient for fuel in this area. Over 2,500 acres of forest already

is deforested to collect wood and establish camps in Chittagong. The risk of tornado, flood and tsunami has increased during and after the monsoon season for this deforestation in Chittagong. Cox's Bazar was the most prominent tourist destination in Bangladesh, with many Rohingya refugees in Chittagong already affected. The hotel business has suffered in the local region due to the extreme Rohingya evacuation since they reported a reduction of around 40% in hotel reservations, even in the span of their sales compared with the prior year (The New Nation, 2017). Bangladesh is a small state with an enduring economy, limited capital, additional population and limited arable land.

Consequently, the tremendous Rohingya flood with its demographic and fast birth levels will seriously hamper Bangladesh's economic growth. The ongoing Rohingya crisis is facing several problems that the people of Bangladesh and the government must be concerned. Let us not ignore that the Rohingya crisis is being stuck in global and international politics itself. If vast numbers of Rohingyans are not resettled to Myanmar, it would be a great challenge for the economy of Bangladesh to restore them. The regional unemployment crisis can also increase at a relatively high rate.

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